

Effectiveness of implantable cardioverter defibrillator as primary prevention in hypertrophic cardiomyopathy: One year follow-up study

Eficacia del desfibrilador automático implantable como prevención primaria en la miocardiopatía hipertrófica: estudio de seguimiento de un año

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Abstract

Background: Hereditary hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM) is characterized by unexplained left ventricular hypertrophy and varied clinical manifestations. The worst outcome of this disorder, ventricular fibrillation, is sudden cardiac death (SCD), hence the only effective treatment is an implanted cardioverter-defibrillator (ICD). Objective: ICD as a significant preventative technique for hypertrophic cardiomyopathy to avoid sudden cardiac death, study ICD shock risk factors and predictors, ICD suitable shock and their predictions. Method: In an observational, prospective cohort trial, 33 consecutive men and women got ICD treatment to prevent HCM. Patients aged 35–64 were examined at Ibn Al Bitar Specialist Center for Heart Surgery in 2017 for one-year follow-up. At ICD programming visits, all patients had transthoracic echocardiography and were compared to a previous echo exam. Results: 33 patients completed the investigation, with a mean age of 46.5 ± 7.1 , lowest age 35, highest age 64, and 1.2:1 male-to-female ratio. Non-sustained VT on Holter, family history of sudden cardiac death, repeated syncope episodes, and left ventricular wall thickness <30 mm increased ICD implantation. 24.2% had two risks, 12.1% three, and 63.6% one. 36.4% positive ICD treatment, all ATP, and all shocks were tested. 27.3% had excellent ICD shock. Women experienced more ICD shocks than men regardless of age. SCD and syncope in the family elevated ICD shock rates. ICD shock risk was higher in women, repeated syncope, and sudden cardiac death families. ICD treatment helps younger patients, those with a positive family history of sudden cardiac death, non-sustained VT, and larger left ventricular outflow tract diameters. Conclusion: ICD shock is more frequent in women with a family history of SCD, syncope, and numerous risk factors. HCM patients with one risk factor may get an ICD as primary prevention. Several risk factors increase ICD shock risk. Inappropriate shock is linked to advanced age and decreased left ventricular outflow tract.

Keyword: Hypertrophic Cardiomyopathy, Implantable cardioverter defibrillator, Sudden cardiac death.

Resumen

Antecedentes: la miocardiopatía hipertrófica hereditaria (MCH) se caracteriza por hipertrofia ventricular izquierda inexplicable y manifestaciones clínicas variadas. El peor resultado de este trastorno, la fibrilación ventricular, es la muerte súbita cardíaca (MSC), por lo que el único tratamiento eficaz es un desfibrilador automático implantado (DAI). Objetivo: El DAI como técnica preventiva significativa de la miocardiopatía hipertrófica para evitar la muerte súbita cardíaca, estudiar los factores de riesgo y predictores de shock del DAI, el shock adecuado del DAI y sus predicciones. Método: En un ensayo observacional prospectivo de cohortes, 33 hombres y mujeres consecutivos recibieron tratamiento con DAI para prevenir la MCH. Los pacientes de 35 a 64 años fueron examinados en el Centro de Especialistas en Cirugía Cardíaca Ibn Al Bitar en 2017 para un seguimiento de un año. En las visitas de programación del DAI, a todos los pacientes se les realizó una ecocardiografía transtorácica y se compararon con un examen de eco anterior. Resultados: 33 pacientes completaron la investigación, con una edad media de $46,5 \pm 7,1$, la edad más baja 35, la edad más alta 64 y una relación hombre:mujer de 1,2:1. TV no sostenida en Holter, antecedentes familiares de muerte súbita cardíaca, episodios de síncope repetidos y grosor de la pared del ventrículo izquierdo <30 mm aumentó la implantación de DAI. El 24,2% tenía dos riesgos, el 12,1% tres y el 63,6% uno. 36,4% tratamiento DAI positivo, todos los ATP y todas las descargas fueron probados. El 27,3% tuvo descarga excelente del DAI. Las mujeres experimentaron más descargas de ICD que los hombres, independientemente de la edad. La MSC y el síncope en la familia elevaron las tasas de descarga del DAI. El riesgo de descarga del DAI fue mayor en mujeres, síncope repetido y familias con muerte súbita cardíaca. El tratamiento con DAI ayuda a los pacientes más jóvenes, aquellos con antecedentes familiares positivos de muerte cardíaca súbita, TV no sostenida y diámetros más grandes del tracto de salida del ventrículo izquierdo. Conclusión: La descarga del DAI es más frecuente en mujeres con antecedentes familiares de MSC, síncope y numerosos factores de riesgo. Los pacientes con MCH con un

factor de riesgo pueden recibir un ICD como prevención primaria. Varios factores de riesgo aumentan el riesgo de descarga del DAI. El shock inapropiado está relacionado con la edad avanzada y la disminución del tracto de salida del ventrículo izquierdo.

Palabra clave: Miocardiopatía hipertrófica, Desfibrilador cardioversor implantable, Muerte súbita cardíaca.

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utations in sarcomeric protein genes cause hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM). The illness is characterised by unexplained left ventricular hypertrophy and clinical heterogeneity. The most significant consequence is sudden cardiac death (SCD), which is especially common and frightening in young individuals¹. This demographic dies most suddenly from ventricular fibrillation. Although no randomised trials in HCM patients, an implanted cardioverter-defibrillator (ICD) is the only treatment that reduces the risk of sudden death². Pharmacological therapy has failed to demonstrate a protective effect³. High-risk individuals who have had sustained ventricular tachycardia or ventricular fibrillation need an ICD for secondary prevention. The remaining patients get ICDs depending on their risk of sudden death⁴. HCM affects one in 500 people⁵. HCM is a primary cause of sudden death in those under 40⁶. Gender does not seem to affect SCD rates, but age does. SCD is more prevalent in younger individuals, particularly those under 35, however up to 20% of SCDs occur in people over 65. Identifying diverse disease patients at high risk of sudden mortality is difficult⁷. HCM is most often inherited as an autosomal dominant genetic characteristic with a 50% chance of transmission. Some instances are caused by de novo mutations, while inadequate penetrance in a parent and, less often, autosomal recessive inheritance may also create occasional occurrences. Patients with family illness are more likely to have a causative mutation⁸. This guideline's clinical entity, HCM, is defined by unexplained left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH) accompanied with non-dilated ventricular chambers in the absence of any cardiac or systemic condition that might cause the patient's hypertrophy^{9,10}. Clinically, HCM is diagnosed by trans thoracic echocardiography (TTE) and maximum LV wall thickness of 15 mm, with wall thickness of 13 to 14 mm considered borderline in the face of additional convincing evidence (e.g., familial history of HCM)¹¹. Nowadays, echocardiography is utilised to evaluate LV wall thickness, although cardiovascular magnetic resonance (CMR) is becoming more used in HCM¹². While HCM mortality is rare, ICD insertion may assist individuals at high risk of SCD. The 2011 ACCF/AHA recommendations emphasise clinical risk factors for SCD. Our knowledge is incomplete. Always consider the patient's

requirements and preferences. SCD risk categorization at first examination and frequent re-evaluation are recommended by the recommendations. Clinical variables have two categories. Established risk indicators are the first group. Some of these indicators alone warrant ICD installation, whereas others need other high-risk traits. Risk modifiers are second. These characteristics assist identify high-risk individuals but are not enough to warrant ICD installation. The evidence connecting established risk indicators to SCD is stronger, although our knowledge of risk modifiers has grown since the 2011 recommendations¹³. SCD risk is linked to TTE LVH severity. SCD risk is highest in individuals with a maximal wall thickness of 30 mm, although few studies have examined severe hypertrophy (35 mm)¹⁴. ICD placement may be oversimplified. Each patient's anxiety, living status, and attitudes on death, as well as the proportional weight of benefits and hazards, must be considered. The poor positive predictive value of any SCD risk factor and the heterogeneity in data strength add uncertainty to SCD risk assessment and severely restrict the application of counting the number of risk factors as the main risk assessment approach¹⁵. Objectives: Evaluation of implanted cardioverter defibrillator as a key preventive strategy for hypertrophic cardiomyopathy to avoid sudden cardiac death, examine probable risk factors and predictors for ICD shock, and study ICD suitable shock and their predictions.

Ibn Al Bitar Specialist Institute for Heart Surgery performed a one-year observational, prospective cohort research in 2017. 33 individuals (men and women) aged 35–64 had ICD treatment to prevent HCM. Ischemic heart disease and dilated cardiomyopathy were excluded from investigation. At ICD programming visits, all patients did TTE and were compared to an earlier echo exam. Each patient with 2-dimensional echocardiographic evidence of hypertrophy and no LV dilatation was classified with HCM. Anti-tachycardia and anti-bradycardia pacing transvenous lead-implanted single-chamber ICDs. All patients got device models with diagnostic memory and electrocardiographic data storage throughout follow-up. Whether recorded data or cycle length data showed ventricular fibrillation or fast ventricular tachycardia (rate 170 per minute), defibrillator shocks or pacing were suitable. Older event defibrillators discharged based on clinical evidence of ventricular arrhythmia. Interventions were judged inappropriate when heart rate exceeded the threshold set due to supraventricular, sinus tachycardia, or device failure proven by ICD interrogation. HCM risk variables determined ICD interventions. History of premature HCM-related sudden death in 1 or more first-degree or other relatives younger than 50 years; (2) massive left ventricular hypertrophy (maximum wall thickness 30 mm), as judged by the managing cardiovascular specialist; (3) 1 or more runs of non-sustained ventricular tachycardia at heart rates of 120 per minute or greater on 24-hour ambula-

tory Holter electrocardiographic monitoring; and (4) prior unexplained syncope judged inconsistent with a This research eliminated hypotensive blood pressure response to exercise due to lack of risk stratification exercise testing. Discrete variables provided by number and percentage, chi square test used to assess (or Fisher exact test if chi square invalid owing to low sample size <20 and if 2 or more with predicted frequency less than 5). Two-sample t-test to compare group means (if both follow normal distribution with no significant outlier). Binary logistic regression analysis used to calculate the odd ratio (OR) and their 95% confidence intervals when the outcome can be categorised into two binary levels, and Wald used to assess which parameters had more strong effect (Wald basically is t^2 which is Chi-Square distributed with $df = 1$), if appropriate probability plot used to present the relationship. SPSS 22.0.0 (Chicago, IL), GraphPad Prism version 8.0.0 for Windows, GraphPad Software, San Diego, California, USA, statistical analysis software, p value less than 0.05 deemed significant.

A total of 33 patients who had hypertrophic cardiomyopathy completed the study. The mean age was 46.5 ± 7.1 , with minimum age of 35 and maximum age of 64 and male to female ratio of 1.2:1 as illustrated in table 1.

Table 1: assessment of demographic data

Variables	Value
Number	33
Age (years), mean $\pm$ SD	46.5 ± 7.1
Gender, n (%)	
Female	15 (45.5%)
Male	18 (54.5%)

The most common cause of ICD implantation was Non-sustained VT on Holter, followed by Family history of SCD, more than or equal to one syncope events, and LV wall thickness ≥ 30 mm. Additionally no Abnormal pressure response during exercise was reported, as illustrated in table 2.

Table 2: assessment of causes of ICD implantation

Variables	Value
Number	33
Family history of SCD, n (%)	12 (36.4%)
LV wall thickness ≥ 30 mm, n (%)	3 (9.1%)
$1 \geq$ syncope events, n (%)	10 (30.3%)
Non-sustained VT on Holter, n (%)	24 (72.7%)
Abnormal pressure response during exercise, n (%)	0 (0%)

VT: ventricular tachycardia, LV: left ventricular, SCD: sudden cardiac death

The majority of patients (63.6%) had only one risk factor, while 24.2% had two risk factors, and finally 12.1% had three risk factors. In the present study 36.4% had positive ICD therapy, all of them had anti-tachycardia pacing (ATP), and all had ICD shocks. 75% of the 12 patients (27.3% of all patients) had appropriate ICD shocks, 81.8% of the patients used beta blockers, and 9.1% received Cordarone, as illustrated in table 3.

Table 3: assessment of ICD therapy

Variables	Value
Number	33
Dose patients received ICD therapy	
Positive	12 (36.4%)
Negative	21 (63.6%)
Number of ICD shock	
2 shocks	6 (18.2%)
3 shocks	3 (9.1%)
6 shocks	3 (9.1%)
Beta blocker, n (%)	27 (81.8%)
Cordarone, n (%)	3 (9.1%)
Appropriate ICD therapy	
Not	3 (25.0%)
Appropriate	9 (75.0%)

Mean EF was $63.3 \pm 5.5\%$, with LVOT 33.7 ± 20.7 mm, and septal thickness of 25.3 ± 3.5 mm, as illustrated in table 4.

Table 4: assessment of new echocardiography findings

Variables	Value
Number	33
Hypertrophy type, n (%)	
HOCM	18 (54.5%)
HCM	15 (45.5%)
LV EF%, mean $\pm$ SD	63.3 ± 5.5
LVOT (mmHg), mean $\pm$ SD	33.7 ± 20.7
Septal thickness (mm), mean $\pm$ SD	25.3 ± 3.5

LVOT: left ventricular outflow tract, HOCM: Hypertrophic obstructive cardiomyopathy, HCM: Hypertrophic cardiomyopathy, EF: ejection fraction

Female patients had higher proportions of ICD shocks compared to male, while age showed no significant differences. Family history of SCD showed significantly higher rates of ICD shocks, also patients with $1 \geq$ syncope events had higher rates of ICD shocks, as illustrated in table 5.

Table 5: assessment of different variables according to outcome of ICD therapy

Variables	Patients received ICD		p-value
	No	Yes	
Number	21	12	-
Age (years), mean SD	45.0 ± 6.3	49.1 ± 8.0	0.120
Gender, n (%)			
Female	6 (28.6%)	9 (75.0%)	0.010 [S]
Male	15 (71.4%)	3 (25.0%)	
Risk factors for ICD implantation			
Family history of SCD, n (%)	3 (14.3%)	9 (75.0%)	<0.001 [S]
LV wall thickness ≥ 30 mm, n (%)	3 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0.284
$1 \geq$ syncope events, n (%)	3 (14.3%)	7 (58.3%)	0.008[S]
Non-sustained VT on Holter, n (%)	15 (71.4%)	9 (75.0%)	0.825
Number of risk factors			
One	18 (85.7%)	3 (25.0%)	0.001 [S]
Two	3 (14.3%)	5 (41.7%)	
Three	0 (0.0%)	4 (33.3%)	
New echo findings			
Septal thickness (mm), mean $\pm$ SD	25.2 ± 3.7	25.6 ± 3.1	0.760
LV EF%, mean $\pm$ SD	64.0 ± 4.8	62.1 ± 6.6	0.388
LVOT (mm), mean $\pm$ SD	34.4 ± 21.9	32.5 ± 19.2	0.806

Female gender (7.5 folds), more than or equal to one syncope events (8.4 folds), and family history of SCD (18 folds), had increased probability of ICD shocks, as illustrated in table 6.

Table 6: logistic regression analysis for assessment of ICD shocks

	Wald	OR	95%CI	p- value
Gender (male)	5.990	0.133	0.027-0.669	0.014
Family history of SCD, n (%)	10.025	18.000	3.008- 107.72	0.002
1≥ syncope events, n (%)	6.190	8.400	1.571- 44.917	0.013
Non-sustained VT on Holter, n (%)	0.049	1.200	0.239-6.025	0.825

OR: odd ratio, CI: confidence interval

Younger patients appear to have appropriate ICD therapy compared to older patients, also patients with positive family history of SCD, those with NSVT, and those with higher LVOT diameter appear to have successful appropriate ICD therapy, as illustrated in table 7.

Table 7: assessment of various predictors according to appropriateness of ICD outcome

Variables	Appropriate ICD		p-value
	No	Yes	
Number	3	6	-
Age	59.7±4.5	45.6±5.2	0.002 [S]
Gender			0.509
Female	3 (100.0%)	6 (66.7%)	
Male	0 (0.0%)	3 (33.3%)	
Family history of SCD, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	9 (100.0%)	<0.001 [S]
LV wall thickness ≥30 mm, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	-
1≥ syncope events, n (%)	3 (100.0%)	4 (44.4%)	0.205
Non-sustained VT on Holter, n (%)	0 (0.0%)	9 (100.0%)	<0.001 [S]
Number of risk factors			-
Two	0 (0.0%)	5 (55.6%)	
Three	0 (0.0%)	4 (44.4%)	
New echo findings			
Septal thickness (mm), mean ± SD	26.0±0.0	25.4±3.6	0.864
LV EF%, mean ± SD	56.0±0.0	64.1±6.4	0.100
LVOT (mm), mean ± SD	14.0±0.0	38.7±18.4	0.009 [S]

Discussion

Young, asymptomatic individuals have a 4–6% yearly mortality rate^[3]. The present study had 0% mortality throughout follow-up.

Preventing sudden mortality in hypertrophic cardiomyopathy patients is difficult. Our research found that ICDs may detect and stop life-threatening ventricular tachyarrhythmias, establishing their function in primary SCD prevention. In Thavikulwat et al trial,¹⁵ 15 of 125 subjects (12%) received adequate ICD treatment (2.6%/year, 95% CI 1.5-4.3%), and the cumulative likelihood of suitable therapy after 5 years was 12.5 ± 3.6%¹⁶. Maron et al. followed 25% of 128 patients for three years. The yearly discharge rate was 7% (5% for individuals with main preventative reason for ICD installation), and 70% of suitable discharges included multiple appropriate treatments^[3], which was consistent with our results. In Maron 2007 et al. research, ICD treatments ended ventricular tachycardia/fibrillation in 103 (20%) of the cohort, and 51 (13%) of the 383 primary prevention patients. Intervention rate was 3.6% each year (95% CI, 2.7%-4.8%); cumulative likelihood of discharge at 5 years was 17% (SD, 2%)¹⁷, lower than our research. Of 104 HCM patients evaluated by Syska et al., 78 had ICDs implanted for primary SCD prevention, 13 (16.7%) had appropriate ICD discharges, and the intervention rate was 4.0%/year¹⁸. In the present study, the mean age of patients was 46.5±7.1 years, with similar distribution between male and female, in Reis et al study which involved 105 patients with mean age 58±18 years, with 53% of the participants was females¹⁹. In Thavikulwat et al study, which involved 135 patients with HCM implanted with ICD, 125 for primary protection and 10 for secondary protection, the mean age of participants was 48±17 years, with 63% of participants was male²⁰. This trial gave primary preventive ICD to individuals with at least one of the following risk factors: 36.4% had positive family history of SCD, 9.1% had LV wall thickness <30 mm, 30.3% had one or more syncope incidents, 72.7% had non-sustained VT on Holter, and no patients exhibited abnormal blood pressure response to exercise. In Thavikulwat et al. study, primary ICD prevention risk factors were maximal LV wall thickness < 30 mm (18 patients, 14%), unexplained syncope (45 patients, 36%), NSVT (77 patients, 62%), abnormal blood pressure response to exercise (8 patients, 6%), and/or family history of SCD in a first-degree relative (24 patients, 19%)¹⁶. The causes of implantation in Maron et al patients with primary prevention of SCD were syncope (41 patients, 48.2%), a family history of one or more SCD (39, 45.9%), NSVT (32, 37.6%), and a left-ventricular-wall thickness of at least 30 mm (10, 11.8%)³. As observed above, the reasons of ICD implantation vary owing to research methodology (ours was prospective cohort, others retrospective cohort) and inclusion criteria. In this analysis, 63.6% had one risk factor, 24.2% had two risk factors, and 12.1%

had three risk factors for SCD that indicated primary ICD prevention. All patients with adequate ICD treatment had multiple risk factors (5 (55.6%) with two risk factors and 4 (44.4%) with three). Similar to our results, Thavikulwat et al. found that most patients had 1 (67 patients, 54%), 2 (43 patients, 34%), or 3 (6 patients, 5%) of the SCD risk factors¹⁶. In Thavikulwat et al. patients with multiple SCD risk factors had a statistically insignificant higher yearly rate of appropriate medication (3.9%/year for 2 risk factors, 3.5%/year for 3 risk factors) than those with a single risk factor (1.6%/year)¹⁶. Maron 2007 et al. found valid ICD discharges in 24 of 173 patients (14%) with 1 risk factor, 16 of 143 (11%) with 2 risk factors, and 10 of 59 (17%) with 3 or more risk factors¹⁷. Patients who got adequate ICD treatment were younger (45.6±5.2 vs. 59.7±4.5 years), had greater family history of SCD, and higher NSVT. Thavikulwat et al. found that patients who received proper treatment after ICD installation were substantially younger (38±11 vs. 49±17 years; P = 0.018)¹⁶. In Syska et al., only NSVT predicted suitable ICD treatments in the PP group¹⁸. The echocardiographic data in this investigation were septal thickness 25.3±3.5 mm, left ventricular outflow tract (LVOT) 33.7±20.7 mmHg, and LV ejection fraction (EF) 63.3±5.5%. Reis et al. measured echocardiographically: interventricular septum thickness, 17±5 mm; LVOT, 36±36 mmHg; LV EF, 64.8±11.8%¹⁹. In Thavikulwat et al. 62% of patients took beta blockers and 3% received amiodarone¹⁶. Our analysis found 81.8% and 9.1%, respectively. Compared to our results, Maron 2017 et al. gave 27% amiodarone and 17% beta blockers¹⁷. Our findings support the use of the implanted defibrillator for primary preventive and lifesaving in hypertrophic cardiomyopathy patients. Despite cardiac mass and wall thickness increases associated with this condition, the defibrillator stopped ventricular tachycardia or fibrillation³. Defibrillators to avoid sudden death in ventricular fibrillation survivors are not controversial. Therefore, selecting HCM patients for primary preventive ICD methods remains unclear. Recognizing several noninvasive risk variables eases ICD decision-making¹⁷.

Conclusions

ICD shock is more likely in women with a family history of SCD, syncope occurrences, and other risk factors. One risk factor is sufficient to implant an ICD as primary prophylaxis in HCM patients, although it is very vulnerable to inappropriate shock. Two or more risk factors enhance the chance of ICD shock. Advanced age increases the risk of inappropriate shock. Left ventricular outflow blockage may cause inappropriate shock.

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